

Creating Authentic Stories in a Cultural Heritage Knowledge Architecture

Modeling 3D reconstructions, replicas and restorations of the Chest of Distress of Maastricht

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A central term in cultural heritage studies that is used to safeguard the original identity of the object during a restoration is “authenticity”. It is a much discussed, even contested term, which has resulted in a wide typology. Some examples of such types are *objective authenticity* (focusing on materials aspects), *constructive authenticity* (focusing on functions of objects in their cultural and historical contexts), *existential authenticity* (based on personal experiences and subjective meanings/values), and *postmodern authenticity* (authenticity as social constructs). (Fredheim, Khalaf 2016; Farrelly, Kock, Josiassen 2019 and Nakonieczna, J. Szczepański 2024).

Laurajane Smith, in her seminal work “Uses of Heritage,” defines cultural heritage as “a process of remembering and memory making – of mediating cultural and social change, of negotiating and creating and recreating values.” (Smith 2006, 56 and 307). One of the processes in which the authenticity of cultural heritage objects and their social and cultural uses are renegotiated is during restorations. In these processes, restoration committee members, restorers, and sometimes the general public balance between old stories associated with the identity of cultural heritage objects or try to underpin the authenticity with new ones as argumentation for (proposed) changes.

Assigning meaning to cultural objects and intangible expressions is often related to stories around a specific site or locus, while the locally produced values of these manifestations should be acknowledged universally (Blake 2002). One of the strategies advocated by international and national cultural heritage policies is knowledge production (UNESCO 1972 and 2003, Council of Europe 1998, Erfgoedwet 2026). We argue that semantic web technologies can play a role in these strategies. The creation of a global knowledge architecture allows for recognizing patterns and similarities that support debates around the question of how cultural heritage worldwide can be safeguarded in an optimal way. Decision-making in restoration practices and the validation of the outcomes hereof can benefit from a digital knowledge architecture based on ontologies that can capture changes in stories of objects in their social and cultural contexts. In order to investigate and assess the impact of changes due to restorations on the original identity of these artefacts and immaterial expressions related to them, we propose modeling various concepts of authenticity.

To this end, we explore the potential of integrating 3D reconstructions of the history and restorations of the 12th century reliquary shrine of Saint Servatius, the so-called Chest of Distress in Maastricht, and its contexts in a semantic web knowledge graph.

St. Servatius Noodkist

Model 3

The original eight panels are now in Hamburg in the Museum für Kunst und Gewerbe (inv. nr 1885-1195g). They were purchased in 1885 from a private collector in Antwerp. The reliefs bear a Belgian import stamp dated 1831-1869.

Fig. 14 St Servatius carries chest with relics from Tongres to Maastricht. One of the panels that originally belonged to the pedestal of the Chest of Distress.

3D model based on restoration drawings of the Chest and Distress in Voyager environment and representation of multiple views on storylines

This shrine is called the Chest of Distress due to the custom since the Middle Ages to carry it around the streets of the city during threats of war, epidemics, or other emergencies to pray for protection. Moreover, the Chest of Distress has played a central role since this period up to now in the so-called Septennial Pilgrimage Processions. During these processions, inhabitants of Maastricht, pilgrims, and other visitors interact with the shrine in immaterial cultural expressions such as theatre plays, concerts, hymns, or in more intimate devotional acts. The (potential) impact of (proposed) changes during the restorations of the Chest of Distress and its public religious roles in processions is illustrative of various types of authenticity brought in as arguments to keep its original identity. Since its last restoration between 1958 and 1962, issues of authenticity were raised again when replicas were considered to replace the original 12th century shrine to avoid potential damage during future public processions. These examples are particularly useful to model the so-called *objective authenticity* based on materiality. However, the presence of the relics of the saints in the proposed replicas also raises questions regarding *existential authenticity* (based on personal experiences and subjective meanings/values). Historical reconstructions of the architectural context of the Chest of Distress in its setting of the Basilica of Servatius resulted as well in discussions about the authenticity of restoration interventions. Ahsmann (2017) developed a hypothetical 3D reconstruction of the original position of the Chest of Distress as part of an altar ensemble before an intrusive restoration in the late 19th Century. His reconstruction is based on a comparative analysis of medieval displays of shrines in so-called altar summae allowing pilgrims to pass underneath and even touch these raised objects holding the relics of

saints. Together with his study of observations of different liturgical customs on special days of the Christian calendar, Ahsmann's reconstruction corresponds with concepts of *constructive* and *postmodern authenticity* focusing on the functions of objects in their cultural and historical contexts and on social constructs. For its variety in concepts of authenticity the historical reconstruction of restorations of the Chest of Distress in various tangible and intangible cultural heritage contexts makes it a suitable case for the proposed modeling. This proposal builds partially on previous publications and presentations by the authors dealing with ontological modeling of storylines to trace the evolution in artworks and copies/ variations hereof (Heuvel, Zamborlini 2021), of interactions of cultural objects with their socio-cultural contexts (Baroncini, Macaluso and Heuvel, 2025; Heuvel, Baroncini 2025)¹ and of uncertainties in the representations of digital 3D models (Baroncini, Heuvel 2026), Heuvel, Baroncini 2026). These extensions to UFO, ICON (Baroncini 2024) and particularly important for the GLAM sector, CIDOC-CRM, are augmented here by models of storylines addressing interactions between various concepts of authenticity, contextualizing identity changes of the Chest of Distress due to its restoration from multiple perspectives. Although this case study is of course no pars-pro-toto for the complexity of the impact of restorations on the original identity of these artefacts and immaterial expressions related to them, the multifaceted character of interventions to Chest of Distress in the various mentioned tangible and intangible cultural contexts provides several starting points to recognize meaningful patterns in restoration histories for further generalizations in ontological models.

We have formulated the following research questions as guidelines for the modeling of storylines dealing with the mentioned concepts of authenticity:

- 1) What are the implications of the restorations of the Chess of Distress in its social and cultural contexts on its original identity?
- 2) Can we capture multiple perspectives on the persistence/loss of its original identity in storyline models due to added/removed parts?
- 3) To which extent can the various concepts of authenticity be used to establish the persistence/loss of the original identity in material and immaterial aspects of the Chest of Distress in these models?

The case of the cultural expressions around the Chest of Distress does not stand on its own. The Meertens Institute's website of shrines and pilgrimages in the Netherlands alone counts 676 places where saints are venerated in public events. The World Heritage List of UNESCO protects, apart from religious processions, also several other types of intangible cultural heritage around objects worldwide.

By modelling the different meanings of the concept of authenticity in such storylines and by exploring integrations hereof in existing ontological models of creative processes, 3D models, and restoration processes, we hope to contribute to a meaningful universal knowledge architecture that can play a role in safeguarding global tangible and intangible cultural heritage.

¹ Ontology available at: <https://github.com/SofiBar/CulturalHeritageHistoricalContext>; Ontology documentation available at: <https://w3id.org/chint/docs/>.

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